

ISic0385

I.Sicily inscription 0385

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 893

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][a]viae av [---]

2. [---]Gêmelius [---]

3. [---][e]t Geme[li][---]

Apparatus

Text after Korhonen 2004 and photo

Ferrara: ...VIAEAV

Dessau: GEMELIVS; Korhonen: GEMELLVS; Ferrara: PCENEITVS

Ferrara: T·P·GEME.

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491596

EDR 139212

EDCS 21900425

Bibliography

Ferrara, F. 1829. Storia di Catania sino alla fine del secolo xviii. Catania. At 380 no.9

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7103 + add. p.992 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 91

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